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Главный редактор:

Ходжиева Дилбар Таджиевна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Бухарского государственного медицинского
института. (Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Зам. главного редактора:

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доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентской медицинской академии.
(Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

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Chief Editor:

Khodjueva Dilbar Tadjiyevna

Doctor of medical Sciences, Professor,
Bukhara state medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Deputy editor-in-chief:

Khaydarova Dildora Kadirovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor of the Tashkent
Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

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Clinic and course options Post-stroke seizures are divided into two categories: early and late, depending on the starting point, i.e., in the first week after the onset of stroke (ILAE, 1981). Early seizures usually occur within the first few days after stroke and are also called "acute symptomatic seizures," whereas late seizures peak within 6–12 months and lead to a higher incidence of recurrent stroke (Bladin et al., 2000, Burnetal., 2000). al., 1997, Hsuetal., 2014, Lamyetal., 2003).

The Classification of post-stroke epilepsy (1962) by G. Barolin and E. Sherzer [6] remains relevant, according to which they distinguish:

- 1) precursor seizures
- 2) early seizures develop in the first 7 days, after acute cerebrovascular accident - stroke;
- 3) late seizures that appear 7 or more days after stroke

Post-stroke epileptic seizures, as a rule, are characterized by a focal onset and occur both with and without impaired consciousness. Motor symptoms are possible, which can develop into bilateral tonic-clonic seizures [2-4].

Sometimes post-stroke epileptic seizures are difficult to diagnose - for example, in the presence of non-motor short-term seizures, lack of correlation between the lesion and the clinical picture of the paroxysmal state, seizures with a generalized or unknown onset, as well as in patients with paroxysmal motor, cognitive, emotional, vegetative and behavioral violations [2].

Such situations require differential diagnosis between epileptic and non-epileptic paroxysmal conditions (syncopal neurogenic, cardiogenic, psychogenic attacks associated with sleep disorders, paroxysmal conditions with dysmetabolic disorders, paroxysmal changes in motor reactions, thinking, behavior, emotions of a non-epileptic nature, etc.) It is necessary to exclude recurrent cerebral stroke or transient ischemic attack[5].

Diagnostic The commonly used definition of epilepsy is the occurrence of two unprovoked seizures more than 24 hours apart (Fisher et al., 2005). The International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) recommends diagnosing the post-stroke variant of the disease in cases of an unprovoked epileptic seizure no earlier than 7 days after the onset of stroke. In this case, it is necessary to exclude all other causes of epileptic activity. For this purpose, the following is carried out:

Neurological examination. Detects neurological deficits resulting from stroke. The appearance of new symptoms in the status indicates a possible different etiology of epilepsy and the need for further examination.

Laboratory research. Along with routine tests, it is necessary to study the biochemical composition of the blood. The cause of epilepsy may be an electrolyte imbalance, the presence of toxic substances in the blood, metabolic products that are normally excreted by the kidneys.

Electroencephalography. It is carried out to assess the electrical activity of the brain. Epiactivity is more likely to be detected in the first 24 hours after a seizure. Epileptiform changes are local in nature in focal epilepsy and bilaterally symmetrical in generalized seizures.

EEG monitoring. Conducted to identify non-convulsive epileptic seizures that are not detected during clinical observation. Can be carried out with simultaneous video surveillance.

Neuroimaging. MRI of the brain is preferred. The study allows us to assess the morphological consequences of stroke, identify tumor, inflammatory, and infectious processes in cerebral tissues. If MRI is contraindicated, a CT scan of the brain is performed.

• **Lumbar puncture.** Necessary for suspected infectious lesions of brain tissue and meningitis. Analysis of the composition and immunohistochemical study of cerebrospinal fluid helps to diagnose the cause of seizures and verify the pathogen.

TreatmentAmerican Heart Association (AHA)/American Stroke Association (ASA) guidelines do not recommend primary prophylactic antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) after stroke, even after hemorrhagic stroke, which has a higher risk of post-stroke seizures compared with other types of stroke. [8 – 11]. However, AED therapy is usually recommended as a secondary prevention measure for developed PIE (post-stroke epilepsy); or in the case of status epilepticus (SE) [7]. In some borderline cases, therapy with anticonvulsants may be required, which should be prescribed individually: acute symptomatic seizures after cerebral infarction with hemorrhagic transformation and the

occurrence of multiple acute symptomatic seizures within 24 hours may indicate short-term treatment with AEDs (more than one month), which may reduce the risk of later seizures and post-stroke epilepsy [11]. If acute symptomatic attacks are associated with a primary cerebral hemorrhage or cerebral venous sinus thrombosis with impaired motility, treatment with AEDs for several weeks may be considered, although there is insufficient evidence to support any general recommendations [12,13].European Stroke Organization (ESO) guidelines [14] recommend discontinuation of AEDs after acute symptomatic attacks, once the acute phase (unit stroke) has passed and the patient has been transferred, but the authors caution that the current level of evidence for almost all treatment recommendations for PIE is very low. Therefore, initiation of anticonvulsant treatment should consider infarction and seizure characteristics, comorbidities, AED adherence, drug tolerability, and drug interactions, among other factors.

Choice of anticonvulsants in the treatment of post-stroke seizures. The long-standing belief that most patients with post-stroke epilepsy can be successfully treated with monotherapy[15] has recently been challenged[16]. This highlights the importance of judicious choice of PIE in stroke patients, who tend to be older, especially with regard to potential drug interactions. In general, clinical studies have shown that new generation anticonvulsant therapies are preferable to first generation anticonvulsant therapies for the treatment of post-stroke epilepsy due to better tolerability and fewer interactions with other drugs [17]. Among the newer anticonvulsants, lamotrigine (LTG), levetiracetam (LEV), and lacosamide (LCM) have demonstrated relatively high tolerability and unproblematic interaction profiles in the treatment of post-stroke epilepsy.

LTG exhibits moderate anticonvulsant efficacy, is well tolerated, generally stabilizes mood, has a low potential for interaction, and is relatively convenient except for the need to slowly increase its dosage to a therapeutic dose. [18]. Recent in vitro data have shown that the sodium channel blocker LTG acts as a class IB antiarrhythmic agent at therapeutic serum concentrations.

Possible pro-arrhythmogenic properties prompted the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) to add a warning to the label [18]. In the absence of clinical data, the ILAE recommends an electrocardiogram (ECG) before initiating LTG in patients with known heart disease, cardiovascular risk factors, and those over 60 years of age to rule out relevant cardiac conduction abnormalities [19]. Most stroke patients fall into these categories, but careful cardiac evaluation, including routine and in some cases long-term ECG, is part of the standard of care for stroke patients, increasing the likelihood that pre-existing heart disease has resolved. have been identified. The ECG should be repeated in patients with cardiac disease at the target dose.

LEV is associated with high anticonvulsant efficacy, low interaction potential, and can be administered intravenously to rapidly achieve effective serum concentrations and be used in patients with swallowing disorders. Adverse reactions after LEV administration occur in less than 10% of patients (irritability and mood swings). In a prospective, open-label study of LEV treatment for late post-stroke seizures [20], 77.1% of patients were seizure-free at one year. Four patients (11.4%) discontinued LEV due to intolerable side effects (fatigue in one patient and aggressive behavior in 3 patients) [20, 21]. In another prospective, randomized, open-label study, there was no significant difference in efficacy between LEV and controlled-release CBZ, but LEV was better tolerated [22].

LCM is generally well tolerated and effective in patients with epilepsy of cerebrovascular etiology [23], and intravenous LCM has been shown to be highly effective and tolerable for nonconvulsive seizure disorder (NCSE) after stroke in patients over 70 years of age [24].

Research results: Gabapentin (GBP) appears to have lower anticonvulsant efficacy and requires multiple daily doses, but has a low potential for interaction. It should be noted that GBP carries a risk of dizziness, dizziness, and altered mental status in elderly patients, especially at higher daily doses [25].

Direct comparisons from randomized controlled trials are not available specifically for effectiveness in PSE. However, the STEP-ONE trial compared LEV, LTG, and controlled-release CBZ as initial

monotherapy for focal epilepsy in older adults using a randomized setting [26]. The study found that retention of LEV at one year was higher than that of CBZ due to better tolerability, whereas retention of LTG was intermediate but not significantly different from either comparator [26]. In the recently published SANAD II trial, LTG showed better 12-month seizure remission than LEV and zonisamide after initial monotherapy for focal epilepsies [27]. Eslicarbazepine (ESL), LCM, oxcarbazepine (OXC), perampanel (PER) and zonisamide are currently insufficiently studied in PSE [28–30]. A randomized pilot study showed that LCM was relatively effective in patients with epilepsy of cerebrovascular etiology, with good tolerance, provided that contraindications (primarily some cardiac conduction disorders) were properly observed.

Conclusions: Monotherapy data suggest superior anticonvulsant efficacy and a favorable pharmacokinetic profile (ie, fewer interactions and less negative effects on lipid concentrations) for LCM compared with CBZ [23]. Randomized trials of antiepileptic drugs intended for the elderly are limited. However, two systematic reviews and meta-analyses suggest that lamotrigine, levetiracetam and lacosamide are the first choice anticonvulsants based on their high efficacy and good tolerability in older adults [25, 26]. In general, older people require lower doses to avoid seizures. For example, an average daily dose of 100 mg of lamotrigine was sufficient to control attacks in many patients [27]. A reasonable strategy for anticonvulsant therapy in the elderly: “Start low, go slow, and stay low.”

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Азизова Раъно Баходировна
Ташкентская медицинская академия
Рахимова Шахнозахон Комилжон қизи
Андижанский государственный медицинский институт

ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОДЕРЖАНИЯ ГЛИАЛЬНОГО ФИБРИЛЛЯРНОГО КИСЛОГО ПРОТЕИНА У ДЕТЕЙ С ПОСТОВИДНЫМ СИНДРОМОМ

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10454066>

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье представлен анализ содержания гипофибриллярного кислого белка при неврологических проявлениях постовидного синдрома у детей. Так было установлено, что неврологические нарушения у детей с постковидным синдромом встречаются в 81,8% случаях и проявляются наличием синдрома вегетативной дистонии и астеническим синдромом. Доказано, что активация показателей GFAP может служить маркером развития неврологических нарушений на доклиническом этапе их проявлений, а при наличии неврологических проявлений постковидного синдрома у детей - предиктором утяжеления течения неврологического дефицита.

Ключевые слова: постковидный синдром, неврологические нарушения, патогенез, глиальный фибриллярный кислый протеин

Azizova Rano Bakhodirovna

Tashkent Medical Academy

Rakhimova Shakhnozaxon Komiljon qizi

Andijan State Medical Institute

FEATURES OF GLIAL FIBRILLARY ACIDIC PROTEIN CONTENT IN CHILDREN WITH POST-COVID SYNDROME

ANNOTATION

The article presents an analysis of the content of hypofibrillary acidic protein in neurological manifestations of post-covid syndrome in children. Thus, it was found that neurological disorders in children with post-Covid syndrome occur in 81.8% of cases and are manifested by the presence of vegetative dystonia syndrome and asthenic syndrome. It has been proven that activation of GFAP indicators can serve as a marker for the development of neurological disorders at the preclinical stage of their manifestations, and in the presence of neurological manifestations of post-Covid syndrome in children - a predictor of worsening neurological deficits.

Keywords: post-Covid syndrome, neurological disorders, pathogenesis, glial fibrillary acidic protein

Азизова Раъно Баходировна

Тошкент тиббиёт академияси

Рахимова Шахнозахон Комилжон қизи

Андижон давлат тиббиёт институти

ПОСТ-КОВИД СИНДРОМЛИ БОЛАЛАРДА ГЛИАЛ ФИБРИЛЛЯР КИСЛОТАЛИ ОКСИЛ ТАРКИБИНИНГ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада болаларда пост-ковид синдромининг неврологик кўринишларида гипофибриляр кислотали оксил таркибининг тахлили келтирилган. Тахлил қилганда, пост-ковид синдроми бўлган болаларда неврологик касалликлар 81,8% ҳолларда юзга келиши ва вегетатив дистония синдроми, астеник синдромнинг мавжудлиги билан намоён бўлиши аниқланди. GFAP кўрсаткичларининг фаоллашиши уларнинг намоён бўлишининг преคลินิก босқичида неврологик касалликларнинг ривожланиши учун маркер бўлиб хизмат қилиши ва болаларда пост-ковид синдромининг неврологик кўринишлари мавжуд бўлганда - неврологик нуқсонларнинг ёмонлашиш предикторлари исботланган.

Калит сўзлар: пост-ковид синдроми, неврологик касалликлар, патогенези, глиал фибрилляр кислотали оксил

Актуальность. Постковидный синдром является актуальной проблемой современной медицины, требующей внимания врачей различных специальностей, учитывая разнообразные клинические проявления и необходимость проведения комплексной

реабилитации пациентов, в том числе детей и подростков [5, 8, 11, 13].

В последнее время увеличилось число публикаций, посвященных последствиям COVID-19, но в большей степени среди взрослого населения. В отношении детей, по-прежнему,

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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